

Evaluation Report

*Critical Cataloguing for Digital Preservation:
a research commercialisation follow-on project*

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Principal Investigator Response

I thank Simon for his detailed evaluation report. I recognise his characterisation of the project from conception to delivery, and I take on board the recommendations made.

This project emerged from two places. First, a sincere and sustained interest in the production, stewardship, and preservation of digital assets, especially born digital data, archives, and collections. The digital preservation community is one that I have always found to be kind, generous, and welcoming, and based on my interactions with them I have been concerned for many years about the apparent underinvestment in the expertise required to effect high-quality preservation. As a historian, I know well that societies do not preserve all that they produce, and as a collaborator with archival professionals I know that there are good reasons for not doing so. I also observe that despite the efforts of the Internet Archive, Digital Preservation Coalition, Archive Team, information scientists, digital preservation professionals (across – largely – the Global North), web archivists, software providers, journalists, community groups, and activists the case for looking after digital data – and especially born digital data – has not always been met with as much enthusiasm as might have been hoped. I am not a digital preservation professional, but I am invested in ensuring that collections of societal and cultural value receive the stewardship they deserve, and so one motivation for this project was to do good work in a space I care about and with people whose expertise I value.

The second origin point for this project is a research interest in the relationship between cultural productions that are preserved – whether physical or digital – and their representation as catalogue information, documentation, or other forms of structured descriptive metadata. Too often, it seems to me, describing, classifying, and arranging an object and/or a collection to facilitate access is not seen as a priority. This is not the fault of those whose professional expertise is to describe, classify, and arrange objects, but rather something – something I've never quite got a handle on – around how this labour has been valued in recent decades. The result is that newly digitised materials have often been appended with 'legacy' catalogue data made in a different time and for different audiences, that investment is made in piloting the use of new technologies to tag, categorise, and – even – summarise large collections cultural assets in ways that, at best, impoverish the art of description and, at worst, produce inequitable and prejudiced outcomes, and that the good practice developed by cataloguing professionals to integrate new thinking, an acknowledgement of their subjectivity, and – even – their inevitable entanglement in the production of new knowledge through cataloguing is unable to be fully expressed. Again, fault here does not seem – to me – to be with those professionals, and as someone who cares deeply about their labour being fully valued I have, over a number of projects, sought to advocate for investment in their craft, a craft that doesn't go away when faced with born-digital materials: the full text of a document or webpage, the technical metadata embedded in a multimedia object, or a statistical summary of a dataset or model does not replace the

need for someone to describe, classify, and arrange those materials, instead it changes the nature and scope of the interventions they might make.

This funding call then offered, it seemed to me, an opportunity to use recently completed work on the latter theme and to combine it with the former. On reflection, that was a big ask and one key thing I take away from the project – and Simon’s evaluation report – is that how that connection worked in my head never quite landed with project participants: perhaps this might have been resolved by holding an open session as part of the call for participants or a kick-off meeting with participants (both of which Simon recommends). Or maybe it was a bad idea in the first place – figuring this out will take more time, effort, and engagement.

Despite this, the level of engagement at the final project event encourages me that my ambitions for the project were not fundamentally misaligned with those of the digital preservation community, that our proposed solutions to community need (such as the prototype AI Assistant tool) have some merit, and that reporting on our findings – as we plan to do – will contribute to richer understandings of the challenges and opportunities faced by digital preservation professionals. This evaluation report indicates to me that the project met its ambitions, even if it did so unevenly. It highlights (Section 2.3) that bringing external voices into digital preservation spaces has benefits. It suggests (Sections 3.2 and 4.2.2) that our approach produced a level of openness and candour that might usefully be reproduced in community development and peer support activities. It also points to opportunities missed by virtue of failing to broaden the range and geographical dispersal of institutions involved in the project (Section 4.2.4). Personally, I do wonder if a greater degree of immersion in the UK digital preservation sector prior to project conception would have been beneficial here (even if doing so would have lessened the apparent value of our wider perspective). These points – and many more – are reflections and learnings that I will take forward in future work. And they may not have been teased out without Simon’s insightful and balanced evaluation of our work, for which he has my sincere thanks.

James Baker
August 2024

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Our aim in participating in the project wasn't so much getting something out of it for our institution, but to participate and contribute to something that will potentially be useful for the community as a whole down the line

cohort feedback

1. Context

This evaluation was commissioned by Professor James Baker, Principal Investigator (PI) for the Project as an integral element of the project.

1.1 The call - arts and humanities-led research commercialisation

The call, published on 14 February 2023, was the AHRC's first opportunity that explicitly sought to increase research commercialisation in the arts and humanities.¹ A sum of £50,000 was available for each award, with the AHRC contributing 80% of the costs and the remainder guaranteed by the principal investigator's institution. Each award was to last 12 months in duration. The call was specifically targeted as follow-on funding for projects that had been funded in the previous two years.

It was anticipated that the projects and their experiences would help shape future AHRC commercialisation activities with the call being seen as the first step of 'new mechanisms and funding opportunities to stimulate research and innovation'.

The eligibility criteria included a call for the application of arts and humanities research and methodologies to adopt an innovative approach to a 'commercial challenge' which might include product design or the creation of a social enterprise or spin-out company. The call was also interested in supporting transfer of benefits from research into a commercial environment. Engagement with potential users and stakeholders was also highlighted as a key component for each project.

Funded projects would have a 'light-touch' monitoring and evaluation framework to identify benefits and impact with learning embedded to develop future commercialisation programmes. Projects were encouraged to identify how learning could be captured in their project.

Projects were asked to submit their 'case for support' and a data management plan. Applicants were encouraged to consider managing the environmental footprint of the proposed activities and welcome proposals that seek to experiment or innovate more environmentally sustainable, as well as inclusive, approaches. Proposals were assessed against five high-level themes:

1. Opportunity and market analysis
2. Project deliverables, costs and resources including the team
3. Intellectual property management and dissemination of project outcomes
4. Route to market
5. Environmental, social and ethical considerations, and wider impact

¹ See <https://www.ukri.org/opportunity/opportunity-arts-and-humanities-led-research-commercialisation/>

The call was accompanied by a guidance document reflecting on Commercialisation of Arts and Humanities Research.² Commercialisation was identified as being:

- a mechanism for making research more sustainable
- an enabler to reaching new audiences outside of the funding application cycles
- that partnerships with businesses, and the public and third sectors can serve as a platform for exchanging knowledge
- contribute to Research Excellence Framework (REF) and the Knowledge Exchange Framework (KEF)

The guidance also identifies a number of barriers why commercialisation of arts and humanities is well behind natural sciences, technology and engineering disciplines. These included communication between academics and commercial partners and the cultural differences between academia and those driven primarily by profits. The hope being that the projects and the wider programme will provide an opportunity to break-down these barriers.

1.2 The proposal

The proposal sought to follow-on the recently completed project concerned with justice-orientated heritage metadata and the links that could be made from this research perspective into a commercial activity. Four specific objectives were identified:

1. To establish the Southampton Digital Preservation Advisory Unit (SDPAU) as a commercial activity that provides training, support and advice particular aimed at small to medium sized GLAM institutions and community heritage groups in the first instance but also corporate and civil institutions. This was to be achieved through the collection and analysis of market intelligence and stress-testing the market including price-point tolerances. A core component would be to highlight the importance of critical cataloguing practices within the digital preservation lifecycle.
2. To enhance the digital preservation landscape by making a novel proposition emerging from their digital humanities background. To establish a cohort from across the GLAM sector.
3. To undertake market analysis including commercial pilots to reach a position of 'market readiness' for the Southampton Digital Preservation Advisory Unit including the introduction of commercial perspectives to critical cataloguing practices.
4. To reflect on the challenges and opportunities of commercialisation in the medium to long-term. To commission an external project evaluation report to measure success against the project objectives and to capture the reflections and lessons learned.

² See <https://www.ukri.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/AHRC-02032023-FoF-Commercialisation-Highlight-Guidance-Doc-v6-FINAL.pdf>

1.3 Reflections on the proposal

A discussion with Professor Baker³ about the proposal was structured around a series of questions and the responses are presented here within this framework and context:

Can you talk me through the construction of the application?

In considering the opportunity, Professor Baker was able to identify a narrative that could serve to link the preceding research project *Cataloguing Legacies*⁴ and the parallel ambition to establish at the University a unit offering digital preservation advice. The approach sought to address the high-level themes specifically highlighted in the call for proposal (see 1.1 above).

In drawing-up the proposal there was a degree of peer review including a discussion with colleagues based in Research and Innovation Services.⁵ The inclusion of external evaluation into the project activities and deliverables was not explicitly required by the AHRC but reflects Professor Baker's personal preference to review and reflect on the lessons learned and to inform future activities.

The principal outputs of the project were identified as being:

1. Website – with background information about the project⁶
2. Case studies – this aspect has evolved into a *DPC Guidance note*
3. Expertise gained through the application of research in a non-academic environment
4. This evaluation report

Why those particular market segments?

The proposal identified “small to medium sized GLAM institutions and community heritage groups in the first instance but also corporate and civil institutions” based upon a number of considerations:

- that larger GLAM institutions were most likely to already have begun to consider the challenges of digital preservation
- that small to medium GLAM institutions would be aware of the need to investigate the issue and potentially looking for external support and guidance including potentially writing a bid or application to secure funding
- that community groups would be aware of the issue and the potential need to identify a source of funding to address the issue

³ Discussion with PI focussing on the proposal was undertaken on 19 April 2024.

⁴ Legacies of Catalogue Descriptions and Curatorial Voice: Opportunities for Digital Scholarship', AHRC, Project Reference AH/T013036/1 had been delayed due to covid, taking 26 months and not the 12 months as originally intended.

⁵ See <https://www.southampton.ac.uk/research/ris.page>

⁶ See <https://critcatdigipres.github.io/>

- Civic institutions is a key perspective at Southampton⁷
- Corporate institutions were most likely to be able to secure funding to address specific challenges of managing and safeguarding born-digital archives

What was the ideal candidate envisaged for the cohort?

The following attributes were identified:

- that digital preservation would most likely be part of an individual’s role or responsibility rather than be focused on digital preservation
- work was likely to have been started and that they might be trying to make the business case for institutional investment to support digital preservation but may have hit a block or barrier to initial conversations about the topic
- that the service may have lost a key member of staff and that this had created or exposed a knowledge gap that needed to be addressed

In terms of size the proposal budgeted for 10 members of the cohort. This was felt to be a significant number of institutions to consult and engage, but also a manageable group to bring together.

What data was envisaged [or needed] to undertake ‘market analysis’?

The principal mechanism for collecting data was always intended to be through undertaking in-person interviews. The decision was taken to avoid issuing a survey or implementing a standard series of questions to ask each cohort although there was a general framework of questions (see Appendix B).

What key stages do you see in establishing the Southampton Digital Preservation Advisory Unit (SDPAU)?

The proposal suggests 5 years to be generating income, with the timing of the application coinciding with writing a business case for the SDPAU. The timescales were a reflection on the need to balance the academic duties and responsibilities with a need to generate income to cover the Unit’s costs.

There was also a reflection that ‘route to market’ was a new concept and a recognition of the learning and development that would be needed to take the steps towards commercialisation.

What risks or concerns did you identify in drawing-up the proposal?

The main risks that were identified during the proposal were very practical ones from a lack of responses when the call for participants was issued to a failure to recruit to the critical role of Commercialisation Project Officer (see 2.3).

⁷ The University Strategy recognises the importance of place “We are deeply committed to Southampton as a city of culture and across the region will further develop our civic role of making a positive impact” see <https://www.southampton.ac.uk/about/strategy/goals>

Knowing what you know now, including from the cohort interviews, are there any aspects that you would change or do differently?

Professor Baker reflected on the term cohort and a recognition that this wasn't helpful as the focus was intended to be on the specific needs of each participant. The term cohort implied a sense of coordinating, managing and engaging the group as a focus of the activity.

There was also a recognition that the proposal and the call for participants features the phrase 'training, advice and support' where perhaps something less specific like services would have been more appropriate. There was also a concern that this phrase might impact the discussion about what the unit might offer before the conversations with the cohort had been undertaken.

One element that emerged from the engagement with the cohort was the high level of continuing professional development opportunities across the sector. This led to the conclusion that demand for introductory training in digital preservation [from the Unit] would be low.

1.4 Successful award

The application was successful with Professor James Baker being notified of this on 26 July 2023 ahead of a formal start date of 1 September 2023.

There does not seem to have been a public announcement about which projects were awarded funding.

2. Commercialisation

2.1 Commercialisation at Southampton

Identifying commercial opportunities arising from the research has been important across the Higher Education sector. Southampton has a variety of programmes and expertise that ensure our students and academics are supported in taking their ideas and inventions to market. The University proudly highlights that its academic teams have formed 77 new ventures since 2000 with its Future Worlds start-up accelerator raising over £7 million of equity investment and employing over 100 people.⁸

The Research and Innovation Services team seeks to provide support to researchers from practical assistance to develop ideas, a state of the art incubation facility at its Science Park, finding business mentors, bringing new products to market and consideration about information property rights.⁹ There is an interesting precedent, with *Arkivum* originating as a Southampton spin-out in 2011.¹⁰

2.2 Market intelligence

As indicated in the proposal, analysis had been commissioned, funded by the Higher Education Innovation Funding, into the viability of the proposed Southampton Digital Preservation Advisory Unit. The brief included the following:

Competitors	Do comparable units exist? If so, what services do they offer? Do they trade in and beyond the UK?
Market	Does the anticipated need exist in the proposed target market? Is the proposed level and nature of service in line with market need?
Training	Does this market have professional development budgets for this activity? Would grant schemes be available to groups/institutions in this market to pay for this activity?
Price	What level of cost can the market bear? Are there more agile competitors (with fewer overhead costs) that would make DigiPres Soton uncompetitive?

⁸ See <https://southampton.ac.uk/business/commercialisation.page> and <https://futureworlds.com/>

⁹ See <https://www.southampton.ac.uk/research/ris.page>

¹⁰ See <https://arkivum.com/arkivum-turns-10/> and <https://arkivum.com/digital-archiving-specialist-arkivum-enters-a-new-phase-of-growth-with-appointment-of-chris-sigley-as-ceo/>

The research was directed beyond the known landscape and contribution of The National Archives and the Digital Preservation Coalition. It identified a number of existing organisations including the International Council for Archives and the Society of American Archivists that were providing support relating to digital preservation.

A range of organisations including small museums, community and cultural heritage groups that had been identified as being active or interested in digital preservation was compiled. A survey was shared, with half of those approached responding and 5 follow-up interviews were undertaken. The interview covered their current context including staffing responsibilities, training, workflows and the tools being used and whether there were planned developments. There were also questions about the particular challenges or shifting priorities that the interviewee foresaw and the possible scope for investment into skills development and the institution's digital preservation capacity.

Respondents identified a wide range of tools being used, potential challenges in terms of expected content and a clear interest in practical hands-on training and Python scripting. There was a clear recognition of the strategic importance of digital preservation. Over 40% of respondents indicated they had no training budget with a similar figure reporting that training budgets were at risk or that a compelling business case would be necessary to secure funds for training.

Some of those interviewed highlighted that digital preservation was not currently a requirement in the Museum Accreditation standard which restricted the impact of any advocacy for training or investment in this area. A high number of respondents indicated the likelihood of applying for external funding to support its digital preservation activities.

Secondary market research

Further research was undertaken to consider which organisations the SDPAU might target with their training and advice offer and to gauge the levels of need within this market. Although over 30 institutions were approached, the response rate was disappointing low which limited the analysis of the responses it did receive.

The 'route to market'

The proposal described a well-established route to market comprised of four phases:

1. Analysis that generates initial insights and estimates consumer demand.
2. The design of a value proposition for a service or product and how it might benefit consumers.
3. Pilots of the service or product to open paths to consumer need, to test price points, and to develop consumer relationships.
4. Scaling the service or product based on insights gathered in phases (1) to (3).

2.3 Commercialisation Project Officer

Recruitment

The position of Commercialisation Project Officer (CPO) was a critical one for the project. As detailed in the proposal this post-holder's responsibilities included the day-to-day client development and liaison in addition to the commercialisation aspects implied by the role title. Even with external funding the normal recruitment processes needed to be followed and it was not until mid-November that the opportunity could be advertised including on the Digital Preservation Coalition website.¹¹

In-post

Joash Johnson was recruited into the CPO post, he had experience of building a digital product and bringing it to market but had not worked in the heritage sector. This meant the adoption of a comprehensive approach featuring distinct research and discovery phases to consider the fundamental question - *What is the problem that we are trying to solve?*

The research phase included reaching out to suppliers and to sectoral organisations including the Digital Preservation Coalition to understand the problem from their perspective. The balance of sector experience from the PI and the commercial perspective of the CPO seems to have worked well in terms of complimentary knowledge, skills and experience. It also placed considerable emphasis on using the cohort discussions (see 3.2) to hear about the challenges and barriers that individuals and institutions faced without any preconceptions or the distraction of validating existing beliefs.

2.4 Southampton Digital Preservation Advisory Unit

The University's website includes a page about the Digital Humanities Lab which features a brief note referencing the expected launch of the unit, now shortened to Digital Preservation Southampton, in the autumn. The new unit will provide "advice and training for organisations on how to build their digital archives, what materials to select, and how best to preserve them."¹²

Outside of this project a Digital Presentation Training Officer and a Digital Preservation Enterprise Fellow have been recruited to support the work of the unit.¹³

¹¹ See <https://www.dpconline.org/news/job-vacancies/vacancy-commercialisation-project-officer-southampton>

¹² See <https://www.southampton.ac.uk/humanities/digital-humanities.page>

¹³ See <https://jobs.soton.ac.uk/Vacancy.aspx?id=39672&forced=2> and <https://jobs.soton.ac.uk/Vacancy.aspx?ref=2410623AR&forced=2> the opportunities were also advertised on the DPC website.

2.5 Comparable units across the heritage sector

Whilst there are a considerable number of digital humanities research units across the UK, there are very few which explicitly mention digital preservation. Even the Digital Curation Centre, which has a very high international profile, describes its focus as being on “building capacity, capability and skills for research data management” targeted primarily at the higher education community.¹⁴

The closest parallel to the SDPAU is that of The Digital Curation Lab, University of Salford.¹⁵ Established in 2019, the Digital Curation Lab seeks to provide a service to local businesses and cultural institutions in the digitisation and digital preservation of their physical and digital assets. The Lab offers a number of postgraduate opportunities including *MRes in Digital Curation* and a *PhD in Digital Curation* and the website details the researchers currently engaged on their academic studies.

¹⁴ See <https://www.dcc.ac.uk/about>

¹⁵ See <https://hub.salford.ac.uk/digital-curation-lab/>

3 Cohort

3.1 Recruitment

A call for participants, detailed below, was sent to a number of digital preservation and heritage sector discussion lists in early November.

Call for participants

The University of Southampton is seeking up to 10 individuals from UK-based galleries, libraries, archives and museums, community heritage groups, or other related organisations who have digital preservation training, support, and advice needs to participate in the 11-month project 'Critical Cataloguing for Digital Preservation' (<https://critcatdigipres.github.io/>), funded by the Arts and Humanities Research Council (UK).

'Critical Cataloguing for Digital Preservation' aims to develop a commercial model for digital preservation training, support, and advice that foregrounds the importance of critical cataloguing practices within the digital preservation lifecycle.

Expressions of interest should be sent to James Baker by email and include the following information: Your Name(s), Your Organisation and a statement (roughly 200-400 words in length) describing your digital preservation needs.

The deadline for expressions of interest is Friday 10 November.

8 responses were received with a number of institutions deciding not to pursue their involvement. After an initial discussion institutions were asked to sign a consent form to confirm their involvement and 5 institutions proceeded as project participants.

3.2 Engaging with the cohort

In-person visits to participants was always intended as the most effective way to gather information and perspectives on the fundamental need of institutions than a less personal video-call. The in-person visit also allowed participants to bring-in additional members of their team. Across the 5 visits a total of 11 participants contributed to the discussions.

Each visit was intended to be an hour long discussion, and in considering the approach it was decided that asking a set series of questions would be too limiting and likely to be less informative than a structured conversation. A series of questions were produced (see Appendix B) and these were used as a guide but were not shared with participants ahead of the discussion.

This approach did seem to make the participants more relaxed than might have been the case in a quasi-interview Q&A session. One unexpected result of this approach

was that participants were very frank and open about the challenges and the difficulties they were facing.

The notes from the discussions were typed-up and analysis undertaken to identify which topic or themes reoccurred across the cohort. One cohort planned to visit the Digital Humanities Lab at Southampton to see some of the hardware it held.

3.3 Reflecting on the cohort

In reflecting on the process Professor James Baker did acknowledge that the cohort could have been broader – the lack of a gallery was cited as an example and whether the use of LinkedIn might have served as a more direct mechanism for engagement than the discussion lists that were used.

The cohort was never expected to be representative of the sector but it failed to secure representation from several of the institution types that had been identified in the proposal. It is unclear precisely why, but all of the institutions that formed the cohort, were located within London and the South East.

3.4 Findings from the cohort discussions

Three core themes emerged from the discussions, relating to what the cohort said they wanted, are detailed below:

1. *Technical knowledge*

- working with a particular piece of software – DROID was frequently mentioned by the cohort but not in a negative context
- acquiring the necessary understanding of the terminology associated with digital preservation
- clear lack of confidence, with many being reluctant (or not confident in their own abilities) to dive-in and solve the problem
- digital preservation being part of their role or responsibilities

With such a low number of participating institutions there is a question as to whether the offer of assistance was more likely to appeal to institutions that lacked a dedicated digital archivist.

2. *Talking with experts*

- whilst recognising there were archives and digital preservation discussion list forums where questions could be asked there were comments that many questions appeared to go unanswered

- The National Archives Peer Mentoring scheme¹⁶ was mentioned, but this supports between 12-14 institutions each year with a six-month project rather than seeking an answer to a specific question or issue. There was interest in being able to access an expert for 30 minutes.

The limited geographical distribution of cohort institutions meant that there wasn't an awareness of groups that have been created to share knowledge on digital preservation including *Midlands Digital Preservation Network* (founded in 2020) and *DigiPres North* which was founded in 2023.

The ask an expert concept is based on *ADPList* which features over 28k mentors who will share their knowledge and experiences and help mentees set goals and develop their own leadership skills.¹⁷ Mentors can be filtered by a range of facets including industry/sector, country and language.

3. Access to equipment/resources

- participants talked about the need to retrieve content from one legacy format [though not a particular format] and whether renting rather than purchasing equipment might be a more affordable way of funding work in this area
- the fear of doing damage to critical content was also expressed as a barrier to developing familiarity with particular tools
- some participants struggled to find test data

These three areas are aspects that the Southampton Unit could potentially offer to institutions on their digital preservation journey. At the outset it had been wondered if institutions would be interested in external support to produce a business case to secure funding. This model is not uncommon in the HE and business sectors but not widespread in the local authority sector outside of larger, often capital projects, for example research and writing an audience development plan.

Comparing this list with initial thoughts at the start of the project shows that there are plenty of CPD opportunities, so less space for the new unit to move into this space. However, the short-term expert and equipment were more unexpected.

Other broad themes

There was considerable discussion about ICT, whose focus quite understandably is on keeping the systems and software the organisation needs up and running. The

¹⁶ For more details about the scheme see <https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/archives-sector/our-archives-sector-role/plugged-in-powered-up/peer-mentoring/>

¹⁷ See www.ADPList.org. It describes itself as a 'global community platform for expert knowledge exchange' a paid for service ADPList Advance sees a mentor receive 90% of the fee paid by mentees.

preservation and long term accessibility of key information assets rarely appears on their to-do list. Some of the problems mentioned were bespoke to a particular institution, discussions also covered commercial and open source software and solutions. One topic that emerged from across the cohort was the impact of having no records management policies, procedures or personnel in-place.

A range of perspective were represented amongst the cohort including services who were keen to retain control over processes and collections. There was also discussion about the sense of feeling restricted by a system which was intended to “do digital preservation” and wanting to get back this sense of control and some concerns about being “locked-in” to that system.

3.5 *Preserving our Digital Pasts: Stories, Methods, Futures*

This one-day event, announced on 3 May, sought to bring together “professionals from digital preservation, cultural heritage, and related fields to share experiences, explore preservation methodologies, and envision future collaborations”.¹⁸

The event, hosted by Digital Preservation Southampton, will feature a mix of talks, panel discussions, and rapid training sessions designed to educate, enlighten, and facilitate networking. We will also announce the launch of our new digital preservation assistant during this event.

Programme

- 10:15 Welcome
- 10:30 Session 1: *One Success, One Failure* - presentations & panel
- 11:00 Break
- 11:15 Session 2: Michael Popham - *DPC's Rapid Assessment Model 3.0*
- 12:15 Session 3: *Introduction to the Southampton Digital Preservation AI Assistant*
- 12:30 Lunch (facilitated use of the Digital Preservation AI Assistant)
- 13:15 Session 4: *Reflections on the Southampton Digital Preservation AI Assistant*
- 14:00 Session 5: *Getting started with email appraisal using ePADD*
- 15:00 Session 6: *Interim findings from the Critical Cataloguing for Digital Preservation project*
- 15:45 Wrap-up and Next Steps
- 16:00 Close

Review of the event

After a brief welcome from PI Professor James Baker, to more than 20 colleagues from 12 different institutions, the day started with three individuals presenting brief case studies about an aspect of their work by highlighting one success and one failure. The format worked really well as there was a balance of reporting activity undertaken

¹⁸ The call included an offer to pay reasonable travel/accommodation costs for UK-based attendees.

alongside reflection of the failure and their cause. There was some similarities across the three presentations and the sharing of practical experiences and accounts of where things didn't go as expected or anticipated was very well received. In the discussion that followed there was clearly a high level of interest in case studies. One person observed that failures were less frequently shared in this way with all likelihood due to the potential impact it may give on a service or teams reputation or discourage potential depositors.

For the second session Michael Popham from the Digital Preservation Coalition introduced the Rapid Assessment Model (DPC-RAM).¹⁹ He highlighted the reasons behind its development and the contribution it can make to planning and advocacy.

Commercialisation Project Officer Joash Johnson introduced the Southampton Digital Preservation AI Assistant²⁰ which had been developed in addition to the project deliverables and was intended to serve as a point of reference or further support. A number of possible scenarios were presented to suggest why a user might look to use the AI assistant including brainstorming for ideas or for assistance with coding.

The tool was received with considerable interest and questions seeking to understand 'what' they were seeing, for example where data was sourced from. One question from the demonstration had resulted in a list of digital preservation systems which led to questions on whether this was ranked by number of users, by recommendations or simply in alphabetical order.

The questions reflected many of the professional issues about any new data source including the reliability of the information, clarity about the sources of information from which it had drawn and that of copyright. Joash highlighted that there were plans to further development ahead of the end of the project (31 July 2024) including the use of multi agents which would expand the features and functionality of the AI Assistant considerably.

Professor James Baker then led a piece of quick training through a hands-on session looking at the email tool ePADD.²¹ Having imported some historical, but publicly accessible, emails colleagues were encouraged to use the tool to dive into the data. The process promoted discussion about sensitive content and the in-built lexicon. Having exported the metadata from the email headers further analysis undertaken

¹⁹ For information, including the freely available worksheets and further resources, about the DPC-RAM see <https://www.dpconline.org/digipres/implement-digipres/dpc-ram>

²⁰ See <https://digipres-assistant.web.app/about> for an overview of the work using Open AI

²¹ ePADD is free open source software developed by Stanford University's Special Collections & University Archives. More recently under the ePADD+ project (2021-2022) Stanford has partnered with colleagues at Harvard University and the University of Manchester to further develop the functionality of the software. For further information see <https://www.epaddproject.org/>

using the *Voyant* tool software platform²² and showed how a number of different perspectives could be gained from the data.

To wrap-up the day Professor Baker then presented the interim findings of the project and how they had reached these conclusions based on external research, user interviews and a follow-up survey. The research identified several elements that were mentioned in the context of being the impact of the situation, barriers and challenges they faced;

1. Organisational constraints including:

- financial constraints including limited budgets
- mismatch of goals between digital preservation professionals and senior management
- many senior managers failing to recognise [or be persuaded about] the importance of digital preservation

The impact of these constraints include projects being delayed or scaled-back due to lack of support, access to appropriate training and the inability to bring-in specialist advice. A further impact of this is the extra pressure this places on staff many of whom find digital preservation as just one of their many responsibilities.

The recommendations to address these issues are to utilise storytelling to engage senior leaders and key stakeholders to highlight the long-term benefits of digital preservation. A second recommendation was to work across the organisation to find others who will advocate for digital preservation.

2. Evolving roles including:

- job descriptions often failed to accurately reflect the skillsets expected (or required) of many professionals
- an unhealthy reliance of online resources and webinars to support in-post learning rather than structured professional development
- considerable fear of accidental but “irreversible damage” to born-digital content
- that the level of help and support available was not similar to that for those managing physical collections
- the evolving nature of technology requires constant upskilling which is difficult alongside other responsibilities, time pressures and the lack of training budget

²² Voyant Tools is open-source software that describes itself as “a web-based text reading and analysis environment” for digital text and is widely used in digital humanities teaching and research. For further details see <http://www.voyant-tools.org>.

A skills matrix (see Appendix C) was presented consisting of three elements – foundational skills, technical skills and people skills concluding that this would be a lot of work for a small team let alone for a single person.

4 Evaluation and observations

4.1 Programme

The call for funding (see 1.1) indicated that projects would have a 'light-touch' monitoring and evaluation framework including a reference to a Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning strategy²³ that does not seem to have materialised. The call highlights the innovative nature of the approach but has not utilised the opportunity to bring the project PIs together – whether formally or informally – to share their experiences.

This project was funded through Round One of the programme and was intended to inform future rounds. The call for Round Two opened in January 2024, just over four months after the first round had started, but with no engagement with the PIs from Round One projects, prevented an opportunity for reflections or lessons learnt to be shared ahead of Round Two applications.

Observation/recommendation

Whilst recognising the intent of the programme, the experience and reflections from this project would appear to be a succession of missed opportunities.

4.2 Review of project objectives

As detailed in the proposal (see 1.2) the project had four clear objectives, each are reviewed and considered in turn.

1. To establish the Southampton Digital Preservation Advisory Unit

Apart from the call for participants and the *Preserving our Digital Past: Stories, Methods, Futures* event the project has had a relatively low profile. The low number of participants in the project and their relative lack of geographical and sector diversity is likely to dilute the strength of the conclusions drawn from the project's conversations and engagement. It also reduced the opportunity to identify distinctions and variations between types of institutions that would have informed the business plans of the unit.

Observation/recommendation

The proposed *DPC Guidance Note* and the AI Digital Preservation Assistant have the potential to greatly increase awareness of the Unit and the services it may offer.

²³ See <https://www.ukri.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/AHRC-02032023-FoF-Commercialisation-Highlight-Guidance-Doc-v6-FINAL.pdf> p7

2. To enhance the digital preservation landscape

There is an opportunity to engage the digital preservation community. The new unit will need to identify how it will place itself into the digital preservation landscape and in particular its relationships with The National Archives, the Digital Preservation Coalition and the Archives and Records Association will be important.

The response to the *One Success, One Failure* presentations and panel discussion (see 3.5) clearly demonstrated the desire of individuals and institutions to both share and learn from the experiences of others.

Observation/recommendation

Adopting this approach earlier within the project timeframe could have served as a mechanism to create a sense of cohort amongst the participating services.

Observation/recommendation

The AI Digital Preservation Assistant (see 3.5) was an additional outcome delivered by the project in response to the specific skills of Joash Johnson the Commercialisation Project Officer.

Whilst recognising this work is still very much in-development the current site has a detailed page about the technical background of the Assistant. To complete the transition from a 'curiosity' to a 'key tool' that supports the digital preservation community it needs to establish its credibility by highlighting the underlying resources that it is drawing-upon.

3. To deepen the impacts of 'Legacies of Catalogue Descriptions and Curatorial Voice'

There is a high level of interest amongst practitioners in cataloguing born-digital archives. There have been a number of initiatives to encourage and share good practice with regard to cataloguing born-digital archives including the *Best Guess Guidelines for Cataloguing Born-Digital Material* produced by the Archives and Records Association Descriptive Standards Roundtable in 2016 and the DPC Technology Watch Guideline by Jenny Bunn *Born digital archive cataloguing and description* in 2021.²⁴ New work and innovative approaches in this area are likely to be widely discussed across the profession.

²⁴ For the DPC Guide see <https://www.dpconline.org/docs/technology-watch-reports/2468-born-digital-archive-cataloguing-and-description/file>

Observation/recommendation

The broad nature of the conversations with the participants meant that it was not possible to focus explicitly on cataloguing practices or to identify and draw parallels with the findings from the previous project.

4. To reflect on challenges and opportunities

Although the range of institutions was quite narrow compared to the broad base that was identified in the proposal the one-to-one discussions proved to be an effective way to get real-world insight into the challenges and the barriers that were faced. A broad range of institutions in terms of geographical location and sectors represented would have allowed a greater level of analysis of the responses and the feedback they received and the needs of specific types of institution.

Observation/recommendation

It is surprising that direct approaches don't seem to have been made to two important target sectors that were identified in the proposal - the corporate archives and community archive sectors.²⁵

Observation/recommendation

Reviewing the institutions that were responding to the invitation to participate in the project against the range of institutions identified in the proposal would have allowed further approaches to be made in a timely manner.

Observation/recommendation

Had the cohort had a broader and deeper range of institutions participating it would have strengthened the evidence that was collected during the project and a broader base from which to launch the Unit.

²⁵ The business archive sector could have been engaged via <https://businessarchivescouncil.org.uk/>, the <https://busarchscot.org.uk/> or the BUSINESS-RESEARCH Jiscmail list. The community archives sector could have been engaged via the Community Archives and Heritage Group <https://www.communityarchives.org.uk/>

4.3 External consultation with the cohort

Discussions with the PI and CPO had highlighted the broad topics that were discussed with cohort members but not the specific details of issues highlighted or the questions raised. A simple online survey was constructed using *Typeform* software and sent to a named contact at each institution who were also offered the opportunity to talk directly about their experiences.

This consultation sought to give the cohort a direct opportunity to provide feedback on their experience, their involvement and the potential impact and benefit of their participation. A summary of the responses that were received is detailed below:

What were the main reasons that you responded to the call for participants?

This question gave cohort members five choices to select and a simple matrix allowing them to indicate whether the issue was a primary or secondary issue or if this was not applicable.

Chart showing the primary and secondary reasons for participation

Whilst recognising the small sample size, the results would appear to reflect a broad range of motives and factors were responsible for institutions expressing an interest in participating in the project. That seeking ‘an external perspective to the work’ scores so highly as a primary reason is no surprise given the widely cited barriers faced by archive services to address the challenges of digital preservation.

What did you hope to achieve through participation in the project?

The responses to this question reflect the wide range of motives behind institution’s deciding to get involved with the project, with reasons cited including:

- *To gain some insight into how our practices are perceived externally (and perhaps through this reflection, improve them), and to contribute to work that will hopefully go on to help the DP community as a whole*
- *To help finalise our newly developed work practices, find a community of discussion, and answer any technical questions we had*

- *I hoped to gain some insight into how others were tackling DP, to learn what was happening at Southampton and to make some connections*
- *We were hoping to engage in knowledge sharing and get perspectives on others working in the field*

Where are you on your digital preservation journey?

This question sought to identify, in the broadest terms, where each institution was on their digital preservation journey. Five options were offered to allow respondents to give a nuanced response and avoid focussing solely on whether they had a digital preservation system (or not), the options were:

- Just starting out (no digital preservation system)
- Developing a business case (no digital preservation system)
- About to procure/implement a digital preservation system
- We have a digital preservation system (but not providing access to born-digital material)
- We have a digital preservation system that is providing access to born-digital material

Unfortunately only two of these options were represented amongst the cohort which were split between “Developing a business case (no digital preservation system)” and “We have a digital preservation system (but not providing access to born-digital material)” with slightly more with-in the latter group. The lack of variation means that it was not possible to identify specific needs for different points on an institution’s digital preservation journey which might have allowed it to delve into an institution’s particular needs at these points in their digital preservation journey.

What were the main topics/questions you raised with James and Joash in your discussion?

- *We didn't really raise issues - we had a general discussion about the DP landscape at [institution], and what support we think we might need to improve our practices (and what technical provisions that might include). We also talked about the groups/people we currently use for support (DPC, TNA)*
- *Lack of stakeholder engagement and concern there was no way to fix this*
- *Forensic capture and workflows*
- *Funding; systems issues; institution support; training*
- *They were asking us about our capacity for implementing systems; politics and personalities around our digital preservation work and advocacy; engaging with researchers and other internal stakeholders; processes and procedures*

Please rate the following aspects of the project

To get a sense of how participants felt about the engagement with the project (as detailed in section 3 above) and they were asked to rate each of four distinct aspects of the project – the initial call, the face to face discussion, post discussion follow-up and the cohort event (see 3.5 above).

For each aspect the options went from 'Very poor' – 'Poor' – 'Fair' – 'Good' to 'Very good'.

Chart showing the rating key elements of Cohort engagement

Whilst recognising the small sample size, the results shows us:

- **the initial call** – a mixed response from the cohort with half of the cohort rating this as 'Poor' and an equal number rating it as 'Good'
- **the face to face discussion** – a wider mix of ratings from 'Fair' though the majority rated this engagement as 'Good' or 'Very good'
- **post discussion follow-up** – a mix of response equally split between 'Fair' and 'Good'
- **the cohort event** – all cohort members who attended the event rated the event as being 'very good' because of the topics covered and the opportunity to engage with other practitioners

What have you done (or are intending to do) as a direct result of the conversation?

The cohort conversation was part of the discovery process for the project but this question sought to hear directly from the cohort if the discussion had delivered any benefits or impact to the cohort themselves. The responses included:

- *It didn't influence what we are currently doing BUT it did give us an opportunity to reflect on our practice up to now. James gave us a few tips on projects or tools which might help us.*
- *Not much from the conversation*
- *Share the results of the presentation from the Cohort day relating to person specifications for DP roles and keep talking to contacts made through the project*
- *It was a good place to reflect on our practices but there are no direct changes as a result*

Even better if...

This question encouraged cohort members to undertake a piece of reflection and to identify something that could have made an aspect of the project even better...

- *Perhaps it would have been useful to have a transcript or summary of our discussion after the fact (although this may be coming). Our aim in participating in the project wasn't so much getting something out of it for our institution, but to participate and contribute to something that will potentially be useful for the community as a whole down the line.*
- *Specific list of assistance that the team could have offered us, which I am hoping will come from the final product set up*
- *Opportunities to meet the others involved*
- *Maybe more opportunity for discussion between cohort members*
- *The initial call / description was unclear on what the purpose of the call was; based on that we were expecting something different to what the face-to-face conversation was*

Any other comments or observations you wish to make or share?

This question simply sought to provide an opportunity for participants to share any final thoughts or comments that had not already shared.

- *The group event was really wonderful. Best part of the whole project, was unclear the purpose of the rest of the project, but this event was so worthwhile. More of these would be great.*
- *Still not entirely clear what the aims of the project were and I don't really feel like I got much out of it*
- *I have benefited from having the opportunity to be part of this project; I understand that this was a 'rapid' project but I do hope that Southampton will be able to look at follow on projects in the future in a similar style; thank you to James and Joash*
- *We enjoyed the conversation and it was very useful to reflect and think about our digital preservation journey, though initially the purpose of the call could have been clearer - we had been expecting the focus to be more on cataloguing*

Observations from the consultation responses

Observation/recommendation

Some participants really enjoyed the opportunity to discuss their experiences and the barriers they faced and found it useful to review and reflect about their digital preservation journey.

Observation/recommendation

There was clearly some confusion about the aims and objectives of the project, with several contributing factors behind this:

- the project title explicitly references cataloguing but this wasn't the focus of the conversations
- the call for participants (see 3.1) mentions "training, support, and advice needs" but Professor James Baker has reflected (see 3.3) on whether a more general term like "services" would have been more appropriate

Offering an open session, as part of the call (see 3.1) to institutions might have provided an opportunity to clearly outline the project and the potential benefits to participants.

Observation/recommendation

There was a particular interest in the sharing of information and the *One Success, One Failure* approach resulted in a balanced sharing of experiences and lessons learnt. The sharing of failures amongst practitioners in the digital preservation community happens too infrequently.

Appendices

A Timeline

Date	Detail
14 Feb 2023	Opportunity announced
25 Apr 2023	Call closes
26 July 2023	Round One projects notified
1 Sep 2023	Round One awards start date
2 Nov 2023	Call for participants [archives-nra]
10 Nov 2023	Call closes
16 Jan 2024	Round Two call opens
10 Apr 2024	Round Two call closes
13 June 2024	<i>Preserving our Digital Past: Stories, Methods, Futures</i> conference
31 July 2024	End of project
1 Sep 2024	Round Two awards start date

	Plan	Actual
Cohort – call	September	November
Cohort – selection	October – November	November-December
Cohort – visits	December – April	February - April
Cohort - meeting	June	June

With a fixed end date the delays in issuing the call for participants meant that the period for visits needed to be contracted.

B Customer Research Questions

Questions prepared for engagement with the cohort (see 3.2) and used to guide the discussions but not directly shared with participants.

Purpose of this Document

To gather initial feedback on the problem areas, structure and flow of the questions, give an overview of types of questions we would want to learn from.

Write this from a personal point of view, encourage them to talk about the key points. Don't feel like they have to talk about everything.

Think about the audience who might not be empowered.

Problem Statement

1. People need to advocate for Digital preservation investment and Budget.
Assisting organizations in understanding and communicating the value and necessity of these practices to stakeholders and decision-makers.
2. There are not enough people to do the work and it's a complex piece of work.
3. There not enough knowledge on Mid to High End Learning Needed at an affordable price.

Research Questions

Stage 1: Short Email Questions

Objective: Gain an initial understanding of the organization's context and leadership's stance on digital preservation.

Can you share a story about how your organization's mission has intersected with digital preservation? What role does preserving digital assets play in this mission?

Purpose: To understand the organization's overall mission and where digital preservation fits within that mission.

In your experience, how do leaders in your organization typically talk about digital preservation? Do they see it as crucial, or more of a secondary concern?

Purpose: To gauge leadership's awareness and priority level given to digital preservation.

What strategies has your organization employed to secure funding or resources for digital preservation? Were these efforts initiated proactively, or was there already allocated budget?

Alternative - *Could you tell us about a time when your organization had to find funding or resources for digital preservation? Was this something you had to advocate for, or were the resources already there?*

Purpose: To learn about the organization's approach to obtaining financial support for digital preservation, whether it's proactive advocacy or utilizing existing budgets.

Thinking back over your time here, how would you rate the resources and staffing for digital preservation? On a scale from 1-10, where do you think you stand now compared to the past?

Purpose: To get a quick measure of resource and staffing constraints in the context of their current situation.

Have you ever faced any challenges when trying to make a case for digital preservation in your organisation? Could you share any particular instances or stories? [Caveat]

Purpose: To identify specific hurdles in promoting digital preservation internally.

Implementation Notes:

- These questions are designed to be concise yet informative, suitable for an email format.
- Responses will provide a snapshot of each organization's current state and attitudes towards digital preservation.
- This stage sets the foundation for more in-depth exploration in the subsequent stages.

Stage 2: User Interview Questions

Objective: Gain in-depth insights into organizational strategies and responses to digital preservation challenges.

Agenda

- Introduction and welcome
- Project overview

Areas of Exploration:

- Organisation and exploring current ways of working

Would you describe your role and responsibilities in the context of digital preservation within your organization? How long have you been in this role?

Purpose: To understand the individual's position and experience level, providing context for their insights.

In your opinion, what are the digital skills or qualities needed to be successful in a role like yours?

Purpose: To understand their perspective on the essential attributes for someone in their position.

What personally motivates you in your work related to digital preservation? Are there any aspects that you find particularly rewarding or fulfilling?

Purpose: To explore their personal connection and passion for the field, which can reveal deeper motivations and satisfactions.

What are the most significant challenges or frustrations you face in your role, especially regarding digital preservation? How do these impact your day-to-day work?

Purpose: To gain insight into their personal struggles and how they affect their work life.

Following up on your response about the importance of digital preservation, could you describe any specific initiatives or projects that have been undertaken to enhance digital preservation in your organization?

Purpose: To understand practical steps taken and how they align with the organization's view of digital preservation.

Areas of Exploration:

- Explore current digital preservation projects
- current challenges with digital preservation.
- Exploring leadership engagement and funding challenges to for digital preservation projects

Questions to explore:

Considering the challenges in advocating for digital preservation, how has your organization managed to communicate its value and necessity to stakeholders and decision-makers? What methods have been most effective?

Purpose: To learn about successful strategies and methods used for advocacy within the organization.

Given the issues related to staffing and the complex nature of digital preservation work, how does your organization approach recruitment, training, and retention of skilled staff?

Purpose: To explore their strategies for building and maintaining a skilled workforce in the face of these challenges.

Can you share an instance where something went wrong in your digital preservation process? How was it handled, and what lessons were learned?

Purpose: To understand their response to failures or challenges and how these experiences have informed their practices.

How does your organization stay updated with the latest trends and advancements in digital preservation? Are there any specific resources or networks you rely on?

Purpose: To assess their engagement with ongoing learning and adaptation in the field of digital preservation.

In terms of technology and tools for digital preservation, what gaps or limitations have you identified in your current setup? How do you plan to address these?

Purpose: To identify technology-related challenges and their approach to resolving them.

Would you describe your role and responsibilities in the context of digital preservation within your organization? How long have you been in this role?

Purpose: To understand the individual's position and experience level, providing context for their insights.

In your opinion, what are the digital skills or qualities needed to be successful in a role like yours?

Purpose: To understand their perspective on the essential attributes for someone in their position.

What personally motivates you in your work related to digital preservation? Are there any aspects that you find particularly rewarding or fulfilling?

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Purpose: To gain insight into their personal struggles and how they affect their work life.

Following up on your response about the importance of digital preservation, could you describe any specific initiatives or projects that have been undertaken to enhance digital preservation in your organization?

Purpose: To understand practical steps taken and how they align with the organization's view of digital preservation.

Stage 3: Detailed Survey Questions

Objective: Collect quantitative, measurable data to identify trends and quantify the challenges and practices in digital preservation.

Overview Questions

- Please select your organisation type
- What is your annual budget for your organisation?

- Types digital collections do you hold
- What is the volume of your digital collection
- How many paid staff do you have?
- How many volunteers do you have?
- Select the number of staff dedicated to digital preservation?
- Does your organisation spend money training volunteers?

Personal Experience and Challenges

- Rate your personal level of satisfaction in your role related to digital preservation (1-5 scale).
- What are the top three challenges you face in your role? (Multiple Choice: Lack of Resources, Technical Challenges, Lack of Training, etc)

Organizational Context and Leadership Perspective

- Rate the importance of digital preservation in your organization's overall mission (1-5 scale)
- How would you rate the level of understanding and support for digital preservation among your organization's leadership? (1-5 scale)
- Has your organization allocated a specific budget for digital preservation? (Yes/No/Don't Know)

Advocacy and Funding

- Rate the effectiveness of your strategies to secure funding for digital preservation (1-5 scale)
- Which channels have been most effective in advocating for digital preservation? (Multiple Choice: Internal Meetings, External Funding Proposals, Public Awareness Campaigns, etc)

Staffing and Work Complexity

- Rate the adequacy of your current staffing for digital preservation tasks (1-5 scale)
- How often does your organization face challenges due to the complexity of digital preservation work? (Frequently, Sometimes, Rarely, Never)

Digital Preservation Practices

- How often are your digital preservation policies and practices reviewed and updated? (Annually, Every 2-3 years, Rarely, Never)
- Rate your organization's technological readiness for digital preservation (1-5 scale)

Responses to Issues and Failures

- How effectively does your organization respond to digital preservation challenges or failures? (1-5 scale)

- What is the most common response when a significant digital preservation issue occurs? (Multiple Choice: Internal Review, Seek External Help, Training/Upgrading Skills, etc.)

Continuous Learning and Adaptation

- Rate the availability and usefulness of professional development opportunities in digital preservation within your organization (1-5 scale)
- How often do you personally engage in learning activities related to digital preservation? (Frequently, Sometimes, Rarely, Never)
- If there were an option for a subscription-based model for ongoing digital preservation support, would your organization be interested? (Yes/No/Maybe)

Potential Services and Willingness to Pay

- Which of the following services related to digital preservation would your organization consider paying for? (Select all that apply: Specialized software tools, Consultancy services, Staff training programs, Digital storage solutions, etc)
- For the services selected above, give us a bit more information about your expectations of what the service should do ?
- For the services selected above, how much is your organization willing to allocate from its current budget? (Options: Below £1,000, £1,000 - £5,000, £5,000 - £10,000, Above £10,000, Not sure)
- Considering your organization's current financial situation, how likely is it to increase the budget for digital preservation in the next fiscal year? (1-5 scale: Very Unlikely to Very Likely)
- What are the key factors that influence your organization's decision to invest in digital preservation services? (Rank in order of importance: Cost, Immediate need, Long-term benefits, Ease of implementation, Staff expertise, etc)

Learning and Information Preferences

- How would you prefer to learn about new developments and opportunities in digital preservation? (Multiple Choice: Online webinars, In-person workshops, Industry conferences, Email newsletters, Online forums and communities, etc)
- How frequently would you like to receive updates or educational content related to digital preservation? (Options: Weekly, Monthly, Quarterly, Semi-annually, Annually).

Marketing

- Where do you find courses and training resources?
- How would you like to learn about new services about digital preservation?

C Evolving Skills matrix

This skills matrix was a key output from the research and shared with delegates attending the *Preserving our Digital Pasts: Stories, Methods, Futures* event (see 3.5).

Foundational skills		
Appraisal and Selection: Evaluating the long-term value and relevance of digital materials.	Preservation Planning: Developing strategies to ensure the long-term accessibility and integrity of digital assets.	Legal and Ethical Considerations: Understanding copyright, data protection, and ethical issues related to digital archives.
Arrangement and Description: Organizing and describing digital content using appropriate metadata standards.	Access and Outreach: Providing access to digital collections and promoting their use for research and education.	
Technical skills		
Digital Forensics: Retrieving and preserving data from various storage media including legacy formats.	Metadata Creation and Management: Applying metadata standards and using tools to manage descriptive and technical metadata.	Basic Programming Skills: Familiarity with scripting languages like Python for automating tasks and data manipulation.
File Format Identification and Analysis: Understanding different file formats and their preservation requirements.	Digital Preservation Tools and Systems: Utilizing software like Archivematica or Preservica for preservation actions.	
People skills		
Communication and Collaboration: Effectively communicating with diverse stakeholders, including IT professionals, researchers, and donors.	Problem-Solving: Identifying and addressing technical and logistical challenges related to digital preservation.	Advocacy: Promoting the importance of digital preservation within the organization and to external stakeholders.
Project Management: Planning and executing digital preservation projects within budget and time constraints.	Adaptability: Staying current with emerging technologies and adapting workflows to meet evolving needs.	

Evolving Skills – Recommendations

Two recommendations emerged from this skills matrix:

- **Prompt Engineering:** digital preservation professionals can leverage ‘prompt engineering’ of AI services to support them in their day-to-day roles. This can support a range of tasks, including creating sample datasets for software testing, generating code for automating tasks, troubleshooting problems, etc.
- **Hiring Practices and Role Descriptors:** digital and born digital content are not going away. Role descriptors across collecting institutions should better recognise (and reward) the digital preservation work that people are doing. Activities relating to work with digital content should be spread across more roles at collecting institutions.